

Synthesis of cinacalcet hydrochloride under solvent-free conditions

Ramadas Chavakula*, Narayana Rao Mutyala and Srinivasa Rao Chennupati

Tyche Industries Limited, H. No. C-21/A, Road No. 9, Film Nagar, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad-500 093, India

E-mail : das.krishnac@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 04 October 2012, revised 04 February 2013, accepted 08 February 2013

Abstract : A simple and convenient procedure for synthesis of cinacalcet hydrochloride by reductive amination of (*R*)-(1-naphthyl)ethylamine and 3-[3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]propionaldehyde using sodium borohydride activated by boric acid, *p*-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate or benzoic acid as reducing agent under solvent-free conditions is described.

Keywords : Calcimimetics, cinacalcet, reductive amination, solvent-free reaction, sodium borohydride, boric acid.

Introduction

Cinacalcet hydrochloride (**3**), an optically active calcimimetic drug, has been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration as Sensiper for the treatment of secondary hyperparathyroidism. A condition characterized by the oversecretion of parathyroid hormone in patients with chronic kidney disease on dialysis¹, has been synthesized^{2,3} by the imine formation of (*R*)-(1-naphthyl)ethylamine (**1**) with 3-[3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]propionaldehyde (**2**) and followed by reduction of the double bond (Scheme 1).

(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]propionaldehyde (**2**), by the reductive amination method⁴ of aldehydes and ketones with solid acid – activated sodium borohydride under solvent-free conditions (Scheme 2). This method allows the conversion of carbonyl functionality to an amine by directly treating a mixture of the carbonyl compound and the amine with suitable reducing agents in a single operation without preformation of an intermediate imine or iminium salt. Sodium borohydride is an inexpensive, safe to handle and environmental friendly reducing agent. This method is not only of interest from ecological point of view, but

(i) Ti(O-*i*-Pr)₄, THF; (ii) NaCNBH₃, methanol, conc. HCl

Scheme 1

However, the process mentioned require the use of reagents such as titanium isopropoxide and ethanolic sodium cyanoborohydride which are highly flammable, difficult to handle and toxic. We now report the operationally simple, highly selective and efficient preparation of **3** from (*R*)-(1-naphthyl)ethylamine (**1**) with 3-[3-2-

also proves to be a clean, rapid and very simple procedure.

Experimental

General : ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ADVANCE-400 MHz, using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent. In-

Scheme 2

frared spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum 100 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electrospray ionization mass spectroscopy was performed using an ion trap mass spectrometer (Model 6310 agilent).

Synthesis of cinacalcet hydrochloride (3) :

3-[3-(Trifluoromethyl)phenyl]propionaldehyde (5.9 g, 0.029 mol) was added to (*R*)-(1-naphthyl)ethylamine (5 g, 0.029 mol) for 10–15 min at room temperature and stirred for 1 h. Mixture of boric acid (1.81 g, 0.029 mol) and sodium borohydride (1.08 g, 0.029 mol) was slowly added lot wise for 1 h at room temperature. Stirred for 12 h at room temperature, completion of reaction was monitored by TLC. After the completion of reaction slowly added aqueous sodium bicarbonate (6 g in 100 ml water) for 30 min. The aqueous layer was extracted with ethylacetate (70 ml). The ethyl acetate layer was evaporated to dryness under vacuum at below 50 °C to get a residue, which was dissolved in hexane (40 ml) and water (40 ml). Slowly added conc. HCl for 30 min to get pH 1 to 2. Stirr for 3 h at room temperature. The solids were

filtered and washed with hexane (5 × 25 mL) and dried to get the crude product. The crude product was recrystallized from acetonitrile to get cinacalcet HCl (7.40 g, 85%); HPLC p urity = 99.66%; melting point : 178–182 °C; IR and ¹H NMR spectra of compound obtained from this experiment is identical with the reported in literature⁵.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Tyche Industries Ltd. for financial support.

References

1. N. Franceschini, M. S. Joy and A. Kshirsagar, *Expert Opin. Invest. Drugs*, 2003, **12**, 1413.
2. E. F. Nemeth, B. C. Van Wagenen, M. F. Balandrin, E. G. DelMar and S. T. Moe, US Pat. 6011068/2000 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1993, **119**, 63054s).
3. L. A. Sorbera, R. M. Castaner and M. Bayes, *Drugs Future*, 2002, **27**, 831.
4. B. T. Cho and S. K. Kang, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 5725.
5. G. Bijukumar, B. Maloyesh, B. S. Bhaskar and A. Rajendra, *Synth. Commun.*, 2008, **38**, 1512.